

IBPG - Darwin

The Institute of Biopaleogeography
named under Charles R. Darwin

IBPG 6 (2021) 1-75

E-ISSN 2956-4573

The occurrence of known genera of fossils in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Tomasz Borowski

The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin,
Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

E-mail address: tomasz.elvis.borowski@wp.pl

The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin

Publisher's Address:

Scientific Publishing House DARWIN at The Institute
22, Adama Mickiewicza Street, 78-520 Złocieniec, District Drawski, West Pomerania, Poland

Cite of this article:

Tomasz Borowski. The occurrence of known genera of fossils in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland. *The Institute of Biopaleogeography named under Charles R. Darwin 6 (2021) 1-75*

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of many years of search for fossils that were discovered at the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie West Pomeranian Province, Poland. The most common fossils found in this mine are Ordovician trilobites of the genera *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822, and *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956, and Ordovician nautiloids of the genera *Endoceras* Hall, 1847, and *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789. Other fossils, such as: graptolites, bactritids, belemnites, ammonites, corals and various types of gastropods and bivalve molluscs, can also be found. The oldest fossils discovered are the Cambrian trilobites of the genus *Agnostus* Brongniart, 1822. This mine has fossils ranging from the Cambrian to the Quaternary. These fossils were transported in erratic boulders across the ice sheet from Scandinavia. Currently, the mine extracts gravel and sand, as well as stones and erratic boulders on an industrial scale, which are then crushed and used as building material in the form of aggregate.

Keywords: Paleozoic, Mesozoic, trilobites, *Agnostus*, *Asaphus*, *Megistaspis*, *Chasmops*, *Illaneus*, *Dalmanites*, *Calymene*, *Odontopleura*, *Ampyx*, *Arctinurus*, *Ceraurinus*, *Achatella*, *Decoroproetus*, *Endoceras*, *Orthoceras*, *Protochonetes*, *Monograptus*, *Bactrites*, *Favosites*, *Halysites*, *Quenstedtoceras*, *Perisphinctes*

INTRODUCTION

There are many gravel and aggregate mines in Central Pomerania. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie (Maps 1-4) (Photos 1-9) is the most diverse and rich mine in fossils. This mine has fossils ranging from the Cambrian to the Quaternary. It is related to the location of this mine in the area of moraine hills left behind by the last Scandinavian glaciation, about 11,000 years ago (Map 5).

The most common fossils found in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie are trilobites of the genus *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822 (Photos 10-13). They are quite common, mainly being found in the form of a tail shield (pygidium). Sometimes an entire specimen of this trilobite can be found, but these are rare cases (Photos 14 & 15).

The second most common trilobite found in this mine are trilobites of the genus *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956. They are the largest trilobites being found quite commonly in the form of a tail shield (pygidium) and, but less frequently, in the form of a head shield (cephalon). A complete specimen of this trilobite has yet to be discovered (Photos 16-29).

Trilobites of the *Chasmops* McCoy, 1849, a distinctive but rare, can also be found. They are found in the form of a caudal and head shield (Photos 30 & 31).

Trilobites of the genus *Achatella* Delo, 1935, distinctive but rare, can also be found. They are found in the form of a caudal and head shield (Photos 32-36).

Trilobites of the genus *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827 are found occasionally but in greater numbers. That is, while breaking down glacial sedimentary stones, the entire grave of these trilobites can often be found. However, a complete specimen of this *Illaneus* trilobite has yet to be discovered (Photos 37-42). Table 1 shows the reported occurrence of the trilobite genera found in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

Table 1. The reported occurrence of the trilobite genera found in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland [1-41].

No	Genus of trilobites
1.	<i>Agnostus</i> Brongniart, 1822
2.	<i>Asaphus</i> Brongniart, 1822
3.	<i>Megistaspis</i> Jaanusson, 1956
4.	<i>Chasmops</i> McCoy, 1849
5.	<i>Illaneus</i> Dalman, 1827
6.	<i>Dalmanites</i> Barrande, 1852
7.	<i>Calymene</i> Brongniart, 1822
8.	<i>Odontopleura</i> Emmrich, 1839
9.	<i>Ampyx</i> Dalman, 1827
10.	<i>Arctinurus</i> Castelnau, 1843
11.	<i>Ceraurinus</i> Barton, 1913
12.	<i>Decoroproetus</i> Pribyl 1946
13.	<i>Achatella</i> Delo, 1935

Trilobites are common with nautiloids. These are represented by the genera *Endoceras* Hall, 1847 (Photos 43-71], and *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789 (Photos 72 & 73). The longest nautiloid of the genus *Endoceras* that was discovered in the Mineral Resource Mine in Mielenko Drawskie was 67 cm long, while the nautiloid of the genus *Orthoceras* had a maximum length of 55 cm [42-56].

These nautiloids are very distinctive and usually well preserved. There is no difficulty in identifying these nautiloids (*Endoceras* – with a dorsal siphon, *Orthoceras* – with a central siphon). The nautiloid of the genus *Endoceras* is often found together with trilobites of the genera *Asaphus* and *Megistaspis*, while the nautiloid of the genus *Orthoceras* is often found with trilobites of the genera *Asaphus* and *Illaneus*.

Brachiopods of the genus *Protochonetes* Muir-Wood, 1962 are commonly found [57-61] (Photos 75-76).

The fossils of various graptolite species are among the basic index fossils, especially in Europe and North America.

Graptolite fossils that are found in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie belong to the genus *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852, being known on all continents except

Antarctica, although in Africa it is known only from its northern part, and in South America and Australia only from single locations [62-78].

Silurian graptolites of the genus *Monograptus* are often found in postglacial rocks in the form of a mass grave together with a nautiloid of the genus *Bacrites* Sandberger, 1843 [79, 80] (Photos 77-86).

The fossilised corals in this mine are found in the form of known genera: *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816, and *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828 [81-83] (Photos 87-94).

Ammonites are found sporadically. Ammonites from the genera *Quenstedtoceras* Hyatt, 1877, and *Perisphinctes* Waagen, 1869 were found [84-87].

Crinoids and belemnites were also found, as well as a wide range of gastropods and bivalve molluscs from the Palaeozoic to the Quaternary.

During several decades of mining operations in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, mammoth fossils were also found. These were mainly mammoth tusks, but in a very poor condition (all photos taken by Tomasz Borowski).

CONCLUSIONS

The occurrence and abundance of fossils from the Cambrian to the Quaternary in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie is the main direction of exploration and research in this field for a palaeontologist. It can be said with certainty that there are still many undiscovered species of fossils in this mine.

Acknowledgments

The author of this paper would like to thank the Management of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie for the friendly atmosphere of cooperation and for making available fossil materials located in this mine for research purposes.

References

- [1] Tomasz Borowski, *Megistaspis gibba* from the Area of Mining Works in Mielenko Drawskie, the Drawskie Lakeland. *Annual Set The Environment Protection*, 6 (2004) 47-54
- [2] Tomasz Borowski. *Odontopleura generalandersi* – a new Silurian trilobite species of the *Odontopleura* genus occurring in the north Poland. *Current World Environment* 3(2) (2008) 213-216
- [3] Tomasz Borowski. *Chasmops* – a typical representative of the family *Pterygometopidae* (Reed, 1905) found in an aggregate mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomerania Province, Poland. *World Scientific News* 57 (2016) 81-90
- [4] Tomasz Borowski, Piotr Daniszewski. New location of the well-known Ordovician trilobite *Asaphus expansus* (Wahlenberg, 1821) from north-western Poland. *World News of Natural Sciences* 34 (2021) 82-87

- [5] Helje Pärnaste, Jan Bergström. The asaphid trilobite fauna: Its rise and fall in Baltica. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, Volume 389, 2013, Pages 64-77, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2013.06.007>
- [6] Pärnaste, H., Bergström, J., & Zhiyi, Z. (2013). High resolution trilobite stratigraphy of the Lower–Middle Ordovician Öland Series of Baltoscandia. *Geological Magazine*, 150(3), 509-518. doi:10.1017/S0016756812000908
- [7] Martin Stein & Jan Bergström (2010) Some lower Middle Ordovician species of Asaphus (Trilobita) from Sweden. *GFF*, 132:2, 105-116, DOI: 10.1080/11035897.2010.486478
- [8] Stein, M., Bergström, J. A complete styginid trilobite from the Ordovician of Sweden. *Paläontol Z* 86, 275–280 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12542-012-0132-6>
- [9] Jan Ove R. Ebbestad, Richard A. Fortey. (2020) Late Ordovician trilobites from the Taimyr Peninsula, Arctic Russia. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology* 18:1, pages 1-135
- [10] Mansoureh Ghobadi Pour. (2019) Ordovician trilobites from Deh-Molla, eastern Alborz, Iran. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology* 43:3, pages 381-405
- [11] Xin Wei, Renbin Zhan. (2019) A new trilobite species from the upper Rhuddanian (lower Silurian) of South China, and its biogeographical implications. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology* 43:1, pages 33-42
- [12] Gutiérrez-Marco, J., García-Bellido, D., Rábano, I. *et al.* Digestive and appendicular soft-parts, with behavioural implications, in a large Ordovician trilobite from the Fezouata Lagerstätte, Morocco. *Scientific Reports* 7, 39728 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep39728>
- [13] Van Roy, P. *et al.* Ordovician faunas of Burgess Shale type. *Nature* 465, 215–218 (2010)
- [14] Van Roy, P., Briggs, D. E. G. & Gaines, R. R. The Fezouata fossils of Morocco; an extraordinary record of marine life in the Early Ordovician. *J. Geol. Soc.* 172, 541–549 (2015)
- [15] Martin, E. *et al.* The Lower Ordovician Fezouata Konservat-Lagerstätte from Morocco: age, environment and evolutionary perspectives. *Gondwana Res.* 34, 274–283 (2016)
- [16] Van Roy, P., Daley, A. C. & Briggs, D. E. G. Anomalocaridid trunk limb homology revealed by a giant Ordovician filter-feeder with paired lateral flaps. *Nature* 522, 77–80 (2015)
- [17] Martin, E. L. O. *et al.* Biostratigraphic and palaeoenvironmental controls on the trilobite associations from the Lower Ordovician Fezouata Shale of the Central Anti-Atlas, Morocco. *Palaeogeogr., Palaeoclimat., Palaeoecol* 460, 142–154 (2016)
- [18] Lerosey-Aubril, R. *et al.* Controls on gut phosphatisation: the trilobites from the Weeks Formation Lagerstätte (Cambrian; Utah). *PLoS ONE* 7, 1–9 (2012)

- [19] Fatka, O., Lerosey-Aubril, R. & Rak, Š. Fossilised guts in trilobites from the Upper Ordovician Letná Formation (Prague Basin, Czech Republic). *Bull. Geosci.* 88, 95–104 (2013)
- [20] Hegna, T. A. The function of forks: *Isotelus*-type hypostomes and trilobite feeding. *Lethaia* 43, 411–419 (2010)
- [21] Boyer, D. L. & Mitchell, C. E. Aligned trace fossils from the Utica Shale: implications for mode of life and feeding in the trilobite *Triarthrus beckii*. *Lethaia* Volume 50, Issue 1, January 2017, Pages 69-78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/let.12177>
- [22] Alfred Uchman, Andrej Martyshyn, Taxis behaviour of burrowing organisms recorded in an Ediacaran trace fossil from Ukraine. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, 10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.109441, (109441), (2019)
- [23] Rudy Lerosey-Aubril, John S. Peel, Gut evolution in early Cambrian trilobites and the origin of predation on infaunal macroinvertebrates: evidence from muscle scars in *Mesolenellus*. *Palaeontology*, 10.1111/pala.12365, 61, 5, (747-760), (2018)
- [24] Seilacher, A., Gibb, S. & Hughes, N. Trilobite trace fossils made for moulting? *Palaeontological Society of India* 60, 27–32 (2015)
- [25] J. Moysiuk, J.-B. Caron, Burgess Shale fossils shed light on the agnostid problem. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 10.1098/rspb.2018.2314, 286, 1894, (20182314), (2019)
- [26] Aria, C. (2019). Reviewing the bases for a nomenclatural uniformization of the highest taxonomic levels in arthropods. *Geological Magazine*, 156(8), 1463-1468. doi:10.1017/S0016756819000475
- [27] Paterson, J. (2020). The trouble with trilobites: Classification, phylogeny and the cryptogenesis problem. *Geological Magazine*, 157(1), 35-46. doi:10.1017/S0016756819000426
- [28] Mats E. Eriksson, Esben Horn, *Agnostus pisiformis* — a half a billion-year old pea-shaped enigma. *Earth-Science Reviews*, Volume 173, 2017, Pages 65-76, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2017.08.004>
- [29] Loren E. Babcock, Shanchi Peng, Per Ahlberg, Cambrian trilobite biostratigraphy and its role in developing an integrated history of the Earth system. *Lethaia*, 50, 3, (381-399), (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1111/let.12200>
- [30] Iliam S. C. Jackson, Graham E. Budd, Intraspecific morphological variation of *Agnostus pisiformis*, a Cambrian Series 3 trilobite-like arthropod. *Lethaia*, 50, 4, (467-485), (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1111/let.12201>
- [31] Sundberg, F. (2020). Trilobite fauna (Wuliuan Stage, Miaolingian Series, Cambrian) of the lower Lakeview Limestone, Pend Oreille Lake, Idaho. *Journal of Paleontology*, 94(S79), 1-49. doi:10.1017/jpa.2020.38
- [32] Arne Thorshøj Nielsen, Magne Høyberget, Per Ahlberg, The Furongian (upper Cambrian) Alum Shale of Scandinavia: revision of zonation. *Lethaia*, 53, 4, (462-485), (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1111/let.12370>

- [33] Claybourn, T., Jacquet, S., Skovsted, C., Topper, T., Holmer, L., & Brock, G. (2019). Mollusks from the upper Shackleton Limestone (Cambrian Series 2), Central Transantarctic Mountains, East Antarctica. *Journal of Paleontology*, 93(3), 437-459. doi:10.1017/jpa.2018.84
- [34] McNamara, K. (1980). Taxonomy and distribution of chasmopine trilobites. *Geological Magazine*, 117(1), 65-80. doi:10.1017/S0016756800033112
- [35] Swisher, R., Westrop, S., & Amati, L. (2016). Systematics and paleobiogeographic significance of the Upper Ordovician pterygometopine trilobite *Achatella Delo*, 1935. *Journal of Paleontology*, 90(1), 59-77. doi:10.1017/jpa.2015.71
- [36] McNamara, K. Evolutionary trends and their functional significance in chasmopine trilobites. *Lethaia* Volume 13, Issue 1, January 1980. Pages 61-78. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1502-3931.1980.tb01031.x>
- [37] Tim Meischner, Olaf Elicki, Ahmed Masri, Khaled Ali Moumani, Mohammad Abdelghafoor Ali Hussein, Ordovician trace fossils from southern Jordan with particular consideration to the *Cruziana rugosa* group: Taxonomy, stratigraphy and trans-regional correlation throughout the Middle East and northern Africa. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, Volume 164, 2020, 103595, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2019.103595>
- [38] A.C. Sandford (2006) Systematics, palaeoenvironments and stratigraphy of the Silurian trilobite *Dalmanites wandongensis* Gill, 1948 and its bearing on the structural geology of the Kilmore area, Victoria. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology*, 30:2, 213-232, DOI: 10.1080/03115510608619314
- [39] Patrick M. Smith & Malte C. Ebach (2020) A new Ordovician (Katian) calymenid, *Gravicalymene bakeri* sp. nov., from the Gordon Group, Tasmania, Australia. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology*, 44:4, 496-504, DOI: 10.1080/03115518.2020.1797874
- [40] Samuel T. Turvey & Derek J. Siveter (2007) Assignment of the South Chinese Ordovician trilobite *Calymene paronai* to *Neseuretus*. *Alcheringa: An Australasian Journal of Palaeontology*, 31:2, 173-183, DOI: 10.1080/03115510701305157
- [41] Bruton, D.L. A systematic revision of *Selenopeltis* (Trilobita: Odontopleuridae) with description of new material from the Ordovician Anti Atlas region, Morocco. *Paläontol Z* 82, 1–16 (2008). <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02988429>
- [42] Olga K. Bogolepova, Björn Kröger, Mostafa Falahatgar, Mojaba Javidan. (2014) Middle Ordovician cephalopods from the Abarsaj area, northern Iran. *GFF* 136:1, pages 34-37. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035897.2014.898328>
- [43] Björn Kröger. (2012) The “Vaginaten”: the dominant cephalopods of the Baltoscandian Mid Ordovician endocerid limestone. *GFF* 134:2, pages 115-132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035897.2012.691897>
- [44] Björn Kröger, Juan Carlos Gutiérrez-Marco. (2020) First record of a nonpaleotropical intejocerid cephalopod from Darriwilian (Middle Ordovician) strata of central Spain. *Journal of Paleontology* 94:2, pages 273-278

- [45] Juan Carlos Gutiérrez-Marco, Artur A. Sá, Diego C. García-Bellido, Isabel Rábano. (2017) The Bohemo-Iberian regional chronostratigraphical scale for the Ordovician System and palaeontological correlations within South Gondwana. *Lethaia* 50:2, pages 258-295.
- [46] Martina Aubrechtová, Tõnu Meidla. (2020) Lituitid cephalopods from the upper Darriwilian and basal Sandbian (Middle–Upper Ordovician) of Estonia. *GFF* 142:4, pages 267-296.
- [47] Aleksandr A. Mironenko. (2020) Endocerids: suspension feeding nautiloids?. *Historical Biology* 32:2, pages 281-289.
- [48] Harry Mutvei. (2015) Characterization of two new superorders Nautilusiphonata and Calciosiphonata and a new order Cyrtocerinida of the subclass Nautiloidea; siphuncular structure in the Ordovician nautiloid *Bathmoceras* (Cephalopoda). *GFF* 137:3, pages 164-174.
- [49] Olga K. Bogolepova, Björn Kröger, Mostafa Falahatgar, Mojaba Javidan. (2014) Middle Ordovician cephalopods from the Abarsaj area, northern Iran. *GFF* 136:1, pages 34-37.
- [50] Harry Mutvei. (2013) Characterization of nautiloid orders Ellesmerocerida, Oncocerida, Tarphycerida, Discosorida and Ascocerida: new superorder Multiceratoidea. *GFF* 135:2, pages 171-183.
- [51] Andy H. King, David H. Evans. (2019) High-level classification of the nautiloid cephalopods: a proposal for the revision of the Treatise Part K. *Swiss Journal of Palaeontology* 138:1, pages 65-85
- [52] Christian Klug, Alexander Pohle, Steffen Kiel, Björn Kröger. (2018) A fossilized marble run: the peculiar taphonomy of Ordovician diploporitan blastozoans from Sweden. *Swiss Journal of Palaeontology* 137:2, pages 405-411
- [53] Jan A. Rasmussen, Svend Stouge, Sarah Gabbott. (2018) Baltoscandian conodont biofacies fluctuations and their link to Middle Ordovician (Darriwilian) global cooling. *Palaeontology* 61:3, pages 391-416
- [54] Anders Lindskog, Mats E. Eriksson, Carsten Tell, Fredrik Terfelt, Ellinor Martin, Per Ahlberg, Birger Schmitz, Federica Marone. (2015) Mollusk maxima and marine events in the Middle Ordovician of Baltoscandia. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology* 440, pages 53-65
- [55] Björn Kröger, Jan A. Rasmussen. (2014) Middle Ordovician cephalopod biofacies and palaeoenvironments of Baltoscandia. *Lethaia* 47:2, pages 275-295.
- [56] Manda, Š., Turek, V. Embryonic and early juvenile development in the Silurian basal nautilid *Peismoceras* Hyatt, 1894. *Swiss J Palaeontol* 138, 123–139 (2019).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s13358-019-00192-6>
- [57] Basal Wenlock biofacies from the Girvan district, SW Scotland E. N. K. Clarkson, D. A. T. Harper and A. N. Höey. Basal Wenlock biofacies from the Girvan district, SW Scotland. *Scottish Journal of Geology*, 34, 61-71, 1 April 1998,
<https://doi.org/10.1144/sjg34010061>

- [58] Fengjie Li, Xuelin Qu, Lingchun Du, Tingyong Dai, Yuchuan Yang, Junwu Li, Chengjin Yang, Genetic processes and environmental significance of Lower Devonian brachiopod shell concentrations in Longmenshan area, Sichuan, China. *Journal of Asian Earth Sciences*, Volume 115, 2016, Pages 393-403, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jseaes.2015.10.021>
- [59] Wang, C., Zhao, G., Li, N. *et al.* Coevolution of brachiopod paleobiogeography and tectonopaleogeography during the late Paleozoic in Central Asia. *Sci. China Earth Sci.* 56, 2094–2106 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11430-013-4670-x>
- [60] Vincent Perrier, David J. Siveter, Mark Williams, Desmond L. Strusz, Thomas Steeman, Jacques Verniers, Thijs R. A. Vandenbroucke. (2015) Myodocope ostracods from the Silurian of Australia. *Journal of Systematic Palaeontology* 13:9, pages 727-739
- [61] Vincent Perrier, David J. Siveter, Mark Williams, Philip D. Lane, (2014). An Early Silurian ‘Herefordshire’ myodocope ostracod from Greenland and its palaeoecological and palaeobiogeographical significance. *Geological Magazine* 151:4, pages 591-599
- [62] Tomasz Borowski. New location of the known Silurian graptolite *Monograptus uncinatus* Tullberg, 1883 in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland. *World News of Natural Sciences* 35 (2021) 56-67
- [63] Andrew J. Wendruff, Loren E. Babcock, Joanne Kluessendorf, Donald G. Mikulic. Paleobiology and taphonomy of exceptionally preserved organisms from the Waukesha Biota (Silurian), Wisconsin, USA. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, Volume 546, 2020, 109631, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2020.109631>
- [64] Rafał Morga, Mirosława Pawlyta, Microstructure of graptolite periderm in Silurian gas shales of Northern Poland. *International Journal of Coal Geology*, Volume 189, 2018, Pages 1-7, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coal.2018.02.012>
- [65] Rafał Morga, Małgorzata Kamińska, The chemical composition of graptolite periderm in the gas shales from the Baltic Basin of Poland. *International Journal of Coal Geology* Volume 199, 2018, Pages 10-18. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coal.2018.09.016>
- [66] Michael Foote, Peter M. Sadler, Roger A. Cooper, James S. Crampton, Completeness of the known graptoloid palaeontological record. *Journal of the Geological Society. Journal of the Geological Society* (2019), 176(6): 1038. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1144/jgs2019-061>
- [67] Tiequan Shao, Chenhui Jia, Yunhuan Liu, Lipu Fu, Yanan Zhang, Jiachen Qin, Kaituo Jiang, Hanhua Tang, Qi Wang, Bo Hu, The Llandovery graptolite zonation of the Danangou section in Nanzheng, Shaanxi Province, central China, and comparisons with those of other regions. *Geological Journal*, 10.1002/gj.3183, 53, S1, (414-428), (2018).
- [68] Michael J. Melchin, Alfred C. Lenz, Anna Kozłowska, Retiolitine graptolites from the Aeronian and lower Telychian (Llandovery, Silurian) of Arctic Canada. *Journal of Paleontology*, 10.1017/jpa.2016.107, 91, 1, (116-145), (2016).

- [69] A. Kozłowska-Dawidziuk, A.C. Lenz, P. Štorch, Upper Wenlock and lower Ludlow (Silurian), post-extinction graptolites, Všeradice section, Barrandian area, Czech Republic. *Journal of Paleontology*, 10.1017/S0022336000031966, 75, 1, (147-164), (2016).
- [70] Löfgren, A. (1994). Arenig (Lower Ordovician) conodonts and biozonation in the eastern Siljan district, central Sweden. *Journal of Paleontology*, 68(6), 1350-1368. doi:10.1017/S0022336000034338
- [71] Sanz-López, J., Palau, J. & Blanco-Ferrera, S. The Late Ordovician–Silurian succession in the Marimanha Massif (central Pyrenees, Spain) and comments on the first the occurrence of the conodont *Kockelella walliseri* in North Gondwana. *J Iber Geol* 44, 641–654 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41513-018-0059-1>
- [72] Corradini, C., Corrigan, M. G., Männik, P., & Schönlaub, H. P. (2015). Revised conodont stratigraphy of the Cellon section (Silurian, Carnic Alps). *Lethaia*, 48, 56–71
- [73] Muhammad Aqqid Saporin, Mark Williams, Jan Zalasiewicz, Toshifumi Komatsu, Adrian Rushton, Hung Dinh Doan, Ha Thai Trinh, Hung Ba Nguyen, Minh Trung Nguyen, Thijs R. A. Vandenbroucke, Graptolites from Silurian (Llandovery Series) Sedimentary Deposits Attributed to a Forearc Setting, Co to Formation, Co to Archipelago, Northeast Vietnam. *Paleontological Research*, 10.2517/2019PR003, 24, 1, (26), (2020).
- [74] Emma R. Hartke, Bradley D. Cramer, Mikael Calner, Michael J. Melchin, Bruce A. Barnett, Stephan C. Oborny, Alyssa M. Bancroft. Decoupling $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{carb}}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ at the onset of the Ireviken Carbon Isotope Excursion: $\Delta^{13}\text{C}$ and organic carbon burial (f_{org}) during a Silurian oceanic anoxic event. *Global and Planetary Change*, Volume 196, 2021, 103373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2020.103373>
- [75] Loydell, D, 2020. Middle Telychian (Llandovery, Silurian) graptolites and biostratigraphy of the Howgill Fells, England, based upon the collections of D.W.R. Wilson housed in the Lapworth Museum of Geology, University of Birmingham. *Proceedings of the Yorkshire Geological Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1144/pygs2019-014>
- [76] Emma U. Hammarlund, David K. Loydell, Arne T. Nielsen, Niels H. Schovsbo, Early Silurian $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ excursions in the foreland basin of Baltica, both familiar and surprising. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, Volume 526, 2019, Pages 126-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.03.035>
- [77] Štěpán Manda, Petr Štorch, Jiří Frýda, Ladislav Slavík, Zuzana Tasáryová. The mid-Homerian (Silurian) biotic crisis in offshore settings of the Prague Synform, Czech Republic: Integration of the graptolite fossil record with conodonts, shelly fauna and carbon isotope data. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, Volume 528, 2019, Pages 14-34, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2019.04.026>
- [78] Natalia Walasek, David K. Loydell, Jiří Frýda, Peep Männik, Robert F. Loveridge. Integrated graptolite-conodont biostratigraphy and organic carbon chemostratigraphy of the Llandovery of Kallholn quarry, Dalarna, Sweden. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*, Volume 508, 2018, Pages 1-16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palaeo.2018.08.003>

- [79] Martina Aubrechtová, A revision of the Ordovician cephalopod *Bactrites sandbergeri* Barrande: Systematic position and palaeobiogeography of *Bactroceras*. *Geobios*, Volume 48, Issue 3, 2015, Pages 193-211, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2015.03.002>
- [80] Marcela Cichowolski, Juan J. Rustán; First report of Devonian bactritids (Cephalopoda) from South America: paleobiogeographic and biostratigraphic implications. *Journal of Paleontology* 2017; 91 (3): 417–433. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1017/jpa.2017.17>
- [81] Tomasz Borowski, New location of the known corals genera (*Favosites* Lamarck, 1816 and *Halysites* Fischer von Waldheim, 1828) in the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland. *World News of Natural Sciences* 35 (2021) 102-117
- [82] Ulitina, L.M., Bondarenko, O.B. & Minjin, C. Evolution of the taxonomic diversity of Mongolian Ordovician-Silurian corals. *Paleontol. J.* 43, 499 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031030109050049>
- [83] Kun Liang, Robert J. Elias, Dong-Jin Lee. (2019) Morphometrics, growth characteristics, and phylogenetic implications of *Halysites catenularius* (Tabulata, Silurian, Estonia). *Journal of Paleontology* 93:2, pages 215-231.
- [84] Harry Mutvei (2014) Shell wall structure and sharp-edged apertural shell margin in the Callovian *Quenstedtoceras* (Cephalopoda, Ammonoidea). *GFF*, 136:4, 531-538, DOI: 10.1080/11035897.2014.901990
- [85] Gregor Radtke, Helmut Keupp, Dieter Korn. (2016) Imbricate radial sculpture: a convergent feature within externally shelled cephalopods. *Palaeontology* 59:3, pages 409-421.
- [86] Harry Mutvei. (2017) Siphuncular Structure in the Extant *Spirula* and in Other Coleoids (Cephalopoda). *GFF* 139:2, pages 129-139
- [87] Arindam Roy, Subhendu Bardhan, Sebabrata Das, Subhronil Mondal, Sumanta Mallick, Systematic revision and palaeobiogeography of *Perisphinctes* Waagen (Ammonoidea) from the Oxfordian of Kutch, India: Stratigraphic and evolutionary implications. *Palaeoworld*, Volume 21, Issues 3–4, 2012, Pages 167-192, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.palwor.2012.10.001>

Map 1. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland.

Map 2. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Map 3. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Map 4. Location of the Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Map 5. The recession (withdrawal) of the last continental glacier from northwest Poland

Photo 1. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie, West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 2. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 3. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 4. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 5. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 6. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 7. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 8. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 9. The Mineral Raw Materials Mine in Mielenko Drawskie,
West Pomeranian Province, Poland

Photo 10. Pygidium – *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822

Photo 11. Pygidium – *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822

Photo 12. Pygidium – *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822

Photo 13(A). Cephalon – *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822

Photo 13(B). Cephalon – *Asaphus* Brongniart, 1822

Photo 14(A). Trilobite of *Asaphus expansus* (Wahlenberg, 1821)

Photo 14(B). Trilobite of *Asaphus expansus* (Wahlenberg, 1821)

Photo 15. Trilobite of *Asaphus expansus* (Wahlenberg, 1821)

Photo 16. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 17. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 18. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 19. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 20(A). Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 20(B). Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 21. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 22. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 23. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 24. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 25. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 26. Pygidium – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 27. Cephalon – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 28. Genal spine (Cephalon) – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 29. Genal spine (Cephalon) – *Megistaspis* Jaanusson, 1956

Photo 30. Cephalon – *Chasmops* McCoy, 1849

Photo 31(A). Cephalon and thorax – *Chasmops* McCoy, 1849

Photo 31(B). Cephalon and thorax – *Chasmops* McCoy, 1849

Photo 32. Cephalon – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 33. Cephalon – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 34. Pygidium – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 35. Pygidium – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 36(A). Pygidium – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 36(B). Pygidium – *Achatella* Delo, 1935

Photo 37. Pygidium – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 38. Cephalon – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 39. Cephalon & pygidium – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 40. Cephalon – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 41. Pygidium – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 42. Pygidium – *Illaneus* Dalman, 1827

Photo 43. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 44(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 44(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 45(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 45(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 45(C). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 46. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 47. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 48. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 49. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 50. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 51. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 52. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 53. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 54(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 54(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 55. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 56(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 56(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 57. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 58. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 59(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 59(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 60. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 61. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 62(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 62(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 63. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 64. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 65. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 66. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 67. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 68. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 69(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 69(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 70(A). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 70(B). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 70(C). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 70(D). *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 71. *Endoceras* Hall, 1847

Photo 72. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789

Photo 73. *Orthoceras* Bruguière, 1789

Photo 74. *Protochonetes* Muir-Wood, 1962

Photo 75. *Protochonetes* Muir-Wood, 1962

Photo 76. *Protochonetes* Muir-Wood, 1962

Photo 77(A). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 77(B). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 78(A). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 78(B). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 79(A). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 79(B). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 80 (A). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 80(B). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 80(C). *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852

Photo 81. *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852

Photo 82. *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 83. *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852

Photo 84. *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 85. *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852 and *Bactrites* Sandberger, 1843

Photo 86. *Monograptus* Geinitz, 1852

Photo 87(A). *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 87(B). *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 88. *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 89(A). *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 89(B). *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 90. *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 91. *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 92. *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 93. *Favosites* Lamarck, 1816

Photo 94(A). *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828

Photo 94(B). *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828

Photo 94(C). *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828

Photo 94(D). *Halysites* von Waldheim, 1828